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Promoting Cooperation Between Teachers And Learners In The Classroom

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ABSTRACT

Education generally and teaching and learning in particular is naturally a relational and social activity that involves people who share different values, beliefs and expectations, a development that makes cooperation key for success both for the teacher and the learners. Regrettably no priority is given to promoting cooperation between the teacher and learners in teaching and learning in the classroom and teachers who should trigger cooperation in learners lack the knowledge and skills for initiating and promoting attitudinal and behavioural dispositions that are supportive and conducive of cooperation between the teacher and learners in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. This development is detrimental to productivity in teaching and learning and needs to be addressed. Using the philosophical research methodology and theoretically guided by social interdependence theory and social constructivism, this study creates insights on the need to prioritize knowledge of cooperation between the teacher and learners in teaching and learning in the classroom, which has immense positive implications for the teacher, the teaching profession and national development of states. In fact, cooperation between the teacher and learners is fundamental and foundational in any meaningful teaching and learning. The paper identifies teachers as critical for innovations in education and recommends that teacher education institutions should shed off their excessive conservatism and unreceptive attitudes to change as well as redesign teacher education so as to educate would-be teachers along lines where skills for relational, interactive, caring and cooperative philosophies can become priorities with their attendant reciprocal behaviours from learners among others.

Keywords: Promotion, cooperation, teachers, learners

INTRODUCTION

One feature that is inherent in man and by extension the human society is the behavioural manifestation and demonstration of curious and innate desires to move forward and this in its practical realization is a complete rejection of the spirit of retrogression and stagnation in any of their configurations. This innate and curious desire to reject the spirit of retrogression and stagnation marks man out as a wonderful

creature with creative and critical potentials (skills), which under right and normal conditions or circumstances can trigger and propel man into receptively and robustly engaging in exploits that are capable of making man participate in co-creation through creating and recreating his environment for his maximum comfort. Inherently, for this to translate into reality, man must constantly embrace and gear up for progressive and quality changes in his social, moral, political, economic, environmental, managerial, scientific and technological endeavours. What bears witness to this forward looking outlook of man is the fact that anyone who takes a curious, conscious and incisive look at the past in comparison with happenings in the present, can quickly come to the consciousness that transitions have always occurred and will continue to occur with rays of illuminations that reflect promises and possibilities of more emerging complex and more sophisticated developments that are likely to emerge in the future, implying that current developments as they exist presently are in their beginning and infant stages, a development that wants man to prepare in readiness for more complex and fascinating developments in the future.

Across develop, developing and underdeveloped societies, one institution that serves as a trigger and instrument for guiding, sensitizing and conscientizing the people in their drive, desire and responses to progressive, desirable and qualitative developments and changes in their social, moral, economic, political, managerial, environmental, scientific and technological advancement of their life is education. Education in these societies is associated with foundational, functional, radical and revolutionary potentials that in addition to adding value, worth and substance to man and his society also has the capacity to bring about formation, reformation and transformation of the individual or group from lower to higher levels.

Globally, education is held in high esteem as a social provision which any parent that considers himself/herself as being impactful and responsible must provide. This aura of importance which education receives stems from the general recognition and belief that education is a fundamental necessity for the survival of the individual and the continuous flourishing of the state (Nwaokugha, 2025:22). Because it is key for the survival of the individual and the state, parents ensure that they provide education for their sons, daughters and wards and consider themselves as monumental, epical and phenomenal failures when they fail to provide it and this attitude of parents towards education is replicated by the state, a development which Shively (2005) acknowledges when he writes that one social services which any responsible state provides for her citizens is education.

The high regard education receives among social services that responsible states and individuals provide for their citizens has made education the epicentre of discussions at village, local, tribal, regional, national, sub-continental, continental and international levels. It can be correct to say that the enviable place of honour which education receives across the globe maybe due to its fundamental and foundational roles in the human capital development of states, the projection, promotion and focus on humane concepts such as democracy, emancipation, liberation, national and human development sensitization and creation of awareness on marginalization, slavery, exploitation as well as the recognition of its provision to citizens as citizens' fundamental human rights. The provision of education as a fundamental human rights of the citizens situates education and its provision at least to a threshold or a basic entry point (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024:61), that can serve as a foundation for the empowerment of citizens without which citizens chances of survival and normal functioning in the society can be impaired. It has to be said and said very unambiguously that the claim that education is a human right is deeply rooted in the fact that its provision at least to a certain threshold for the citizens can serve as a springboard and foundation that has potentials to empower citizens in any endeavours of their choice later in life. The idea of providing intellectual empowerment upon which education as a human right revolves invokes an aura of moral responsibility and moral rationality on parents as well as on the state to provide education for the citizens as a fundamental requirement for the survival of the individual and the sustainable development of the state, a development, which when viewed critically is in the best interests of parents and the state. No individual and no state that is desirous of genuine development or advancement to enviable heights can achieve such lofty dreams without meaningful and qualitative investments in the education of the younger ones, who are the beacon of hope through which the dreams and aspirations of the individual and

the state can be translated into reality. In fact, a comprehensive and inclusive justification of education as a human right derives impetus according to Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:155),

From the fact that education as a social provision is a foundational and fundamental necessity for the well-being and optimal functioning of the individual and the state with the guiding operational principle for the intensification of its provision being that any individual that has been provided his rights to education has been empowered with skills and dispositions for adapting, navigating and responding to changes and challenges in an ever-changing complex world, especially the imbibing and demonstration of positive changes that can bring about reformation and transformation of the individual and his state in direction that can enhance the individual's quality contributions to his personal survival and sustainable development of his society and state.

True, all the foregoing narratives about education reveal that education is a necessary and fundamental gateway for progressive growth and development, key for unlocking doors that block opportunities, a social provision for reforms and transformations, foundation for developing creative and critical consciousness in citizens through which radical revolutions for liberation, emancipation, empowerment and wealth creation can be initiated and equally a beacon of hope for challenging structural injustices, structural inequalities, poverty, marginalization, deprivation and many other forms of behaviours that are antithetical to genuine human capital development, human capacity building and national development. This is the non-neutrality of education or the ambivalent nature of education, which Eboh (1996:130), acknowledges when she writes that education "can serve as mere socialization whose essential duty is to preserve and perpetuate the status quo" or "serve as an eye-opener by awakening critical consciousness". Education and its provision takes place in multifaceted settings but many scholars and institution pay particular attention to formal education where education takes place in formal settings in schools, colleges and universities usually in what Nwaokugha (2025:23) calls instructional and learning space called the classroom. The classroom is associated with being a communication, interaction and instructional space where learners assemble for learning and instruction under a teacher, who professionally initiates pedagogical actions and activities that are supportive of meaningful, impactful and quality teaching and learning. The classroom as a communication, interaction and instructional space is epically and phenomenally known for its unpredictable, simultaneous and future directed multifaceted actions and activities from the teacher and learners. Part of what accounts for this is that learners who assemble in the classroom for learning purposes have different approaches to learning, have different beliefs, have different value systems and come from different backgrounds but one factor which all learners in the classroom try to share in common is their inclination to wish or to aspire to benefit maximally from the actions and activities of the teacher in the classroom.

For any meaningful and impactful teaching by the teacher and learning by the learner to be achieved in any classroom where these differences exist, the teacher must create and maintain a cooperative and supportive environment where the behaviour of the learners must receptively align with order, normalcy and decorum, where morally acceptable social norms that can guarantee positive changes, reforms and transformations in desirable directions can prevail so that the teacher can achieve his objectives and the learners can individually and collectively make meaningful impacts in reforming and transforming the society for the common good of humanity. This points in the direction that teacher's sustenance, maintenance and manipulation of variables in the classroom is fundamentally and foundationally necessary to ensure the prevalence of an environment that is supportive of impactful, meaningful and effective teaching and learning. In other words, orderly environment and orderly behaviour from all the stakeholders in the classroom is a foundational and fundamental requirement for success in any impactful and meaningful teaching and learning situation as the professional expertise, superlative mastery of content or subject matter by a teacher and the readiness of learners to learn can translate to zero where an atmosphere of cooperation between the teacher and his learners is missing in the classroom.

It is a fact that cannot be doubted that teaching and learning is a relational activity and this unique trait of teaching and learning situates cooperation between the teacher and the learners at the heart of any impactful teaching and learning experience. This assertion is in line with da luz (2015:2), who writes that

“the best productivity in a classroom comes from effective cooperation between the teacher and the students”. Cooperation in teaching and learning is a multi-sided phenomenon that has multi-dimensional directions, and in all these, it has potentials to support teachers and learners to realize their objectives and ambition in life. It may be on account of these multidimensional capacities that Klasnic, Duranovic and Maras (2020:21), write that cooperation between students realises quality peer relationships’ and one can add that cooperation between the teacher and learners promotes and encourages the highest levels of achievement and productivity and is supportive of the development of the right moral, social and emotional development of the learners in any meaningful and impactful teaching and learning situation. What brings out the truth and reality of the above assertion is the fact that learners spend more quality time in the classroom, including spending more quality time with teachers in the school than with their parents in their respective homes. The fact that learners spend more quality time in the classroom with their teachers make case for the intensification of efforts that can support and promote cooperation between the teacher and his learners and narratives in support of this instructional pedagogical and epistemological paradigm shift and innovation points in the direction that the person who should be at the helm of affairs to initiate all the necessary supportive conditions that can stimulate in learners all the behavioural dispositions that are supportive of cooperation in teaching and learning in the classroom is the teacher and gloriously teachers who consciously and unconsciously develop and initiate cooperative and supportive environments in the course of teaching and learning systematically and receptively uplift and step up the teaching profession and the professional role of teachers to enviable heights. As obvious as this can be, a worrisome trend and a cause for concern is that most teachers across all tiers of the education system especially in developing and underdeveloped countries phenomenally lack pedagogical skills for promoting cooperation and other relational traits between them and their learners, a development that terribly lowers the motivation, enthusiasm and zeal that can stimulate curiosity in any impactful and meaningful teaching and learning in the classroom. Confirming this regrettable development, Lawrence S. Finkel, a past President of Association for Supervision and Curriculum hit the nail on the head when he noted “that teachers rarely provide for cooperative practices to take place in the classroom”. One must point out that this deficit monumentally and epically undermines the level of productivity and success of the teacher in his teaching and equally undermines the level of achievement of the learners from their participation in learning experiences. Efforts to address issues that undermine teachers’ productivity in teaching and learning and efforts to equally address factors that undermine learners’ efforts to maximally achieve from their participation in teaching and learning experiences or activities should deserve the highest attention of any authority in education. Therefore, this study specifically focuses on discussing strategies for promoting cooperation between teachers and learners in the classroom.

This study can be significant in a number of ways. As many studies have exclusively focused on cooperation and collaboration among teachers, this study can break frontiers by adding new narratives on strategies that can lead to achieving higher productivity among teachers and higher achievements among learners in the classroom. In fact, the study is innovative and contemporary and correspondingly promises creating robust insights on pedagogical actions and activities the teacher can initiate so as to sustain supportive environments that can be conducive for higher productivity and higher achievement for learners in the classroom. The study can help raise the bar in terms of behavioural expectations teachers and learners can individually and collectively showcase in the classroom that can enable teachers to maximally deliver instructions and for learners to maximally benefit from every learning experience provided by the teacher. The study can trigger radical epistemological revolutions and new beginnings in teacher education, professional re-education of teachers, policy formulation and implementation whereby teachers can be educated to look inwards for answers to the many issues that hinder effective interaction, effective relations and effective communication in the course of teaching and learning in the classroom. This can be signalling a new consciousness where the teacher exploits and exercises his authority in identifying and contributing to the development of policies for solving problems in education as against the current practice where directives are issued to him from above to implement without his inputs.

Specifically, the significance of this study lies in its ability to add to new pedagogical theorizing and practice as well as contribute to innovation and contemporary ideas that can particularly guide teachers, philosophers, educational planners and managers, administrators of schools, researchers, policy makers and learners to gain useful insights that have potentials to promote best global practices in teaching and learning.

In the area of theoretical framework, two theories namely social interdependence theory and social constructivism guided this study. Scholars have diversified but related historical and psychological roots of social interdependence theory. However, all such diversified historical and psychological roots point in one direction namely; social interdependence theory rests on the premise that in the pursuit of knowledge particularly in teaching and learning, no person is an island, no person is a sole authority and no person is so dispensable to the point of not being able to make any impactful, meaningful and quality contributions that can impact or influence actions and activities in the teaching learning process. This translates to mean that social interdependence theory invokes a meaning that rests on the thesis that the actions and activities of members of a group can systematically affect positively or negatively the successes, failures, actions and activities of other members of the group. Correspondingly, social interdependence theory subscribes to the fact that exchange of ideas between teacher and teacher, teacher and learners and among learners or peer interactions and relationships are essential drivers and necessary conditions for impactful, meaningful and effective teaching and learning.

What had been said above can be said differently to mean that the main idea of social interdependence theory is that the goal and objective of an individual in a group setting has the ability, capacity and potential to affect how individuals in a group interact and consequently such systems of interactions among members of a group can fundamentally, foundationally and potentially affect actions, activities, goals and achievements within a group. This means in the education industry, productivity in teaching and learning or the level of teaching and learning can phenomenally skyrocket where every stakeholder in the teaching and learning business understands that the actions and activities of one person in the teaching and learning business or enterprise is functionally and fundamentally essential for the collective success or otherwise of any person in the group. It can be said that teaching and learning is a focal flashpoint where the actions and activities of one person in the classroom has multiple ways of positively or negatively affecting not only the actions, activities or behaviours of the initiators of an action or activity but the actions and activities of other members in the same classroom. This may account for why Johnson and Johnson (2009), write that social interdependence theory provides foundations upon which cooperative learning is built and this assumption may derive justification from the fact that social interdependence theory principally exists in situations where the interests and goals other persons directly and indirectly affect the goals and interests of others in a group setting.

Social interdependence theory posits that interdependence can produce positive or negative influences on the members of a group. It can produce positive actions or results when interactions among members of a group, facilitate or lead to the attainment of group members' goals and objectives and negative actions or results when interactions favour ones' goal attainment by hindering the attainment of the objectives and goals of other group members. We must note that actions and activities that derive from negative interdependence usually introduce competition or competitive behaviours among members of a group and we must also note that social interdependence theory is instrumental in promoting cooperation on one hand and competition on the other.

Social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction holds that creative insights, creative ingenuity, creativity and critical consciousness of man are the basic foundations and pillars of whatever knowledge that exists in any discipline in any society. This simply means that human beings are the architects, builders and constructors (Nwaokugha & Odinka, 2025:180) of whatever knowledge and the trajectories through which this translates into reality are the various day to day experience and interactions of man with his fellow man, institutions and phenomena in the society.

It is important we point out that the emphasis on creative foresight, creative ingenuity and critical consciousness of man or whosoever is desirous of producing or generating knowledge, confirming

knowledge, expanding or extending the frontiers or boundaries of knowledge or refuting knowledge must use his brain or appeal to his God-given innate abilities to drive his case. This is the key focal flashpoint which Liu and Matthew (2005:387) acknowledge when they write that “knowledge is not mechanically acquired but constructed with the constraints and offerings of the learning environment”. In fact, Nwaokugha (2025:24) unambiguously simplifies the meaning and understanding of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction when he writes that:

What is at the heart or centre of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is the awareness that no knowledge of any configuration is ready made and correspondingly sampled or displayed anywhere to be purchased or hired by who wants it, rather knowledge of any configuration can be produced, generated and constructed through the conscious, critical and creative efforts of an individual or individuals who demonstrate creative engagement, commitment and critical consciousness in the search for knowledge.

What the above exposes is that there are core behavioural or attitudinal dispositions which any one or institution that is desirous of producing, constructing and generating knowledge must fulfil or showcase and these attitudinal or behavioural dispositions which the individual or institution must showcase include the ability to demonstrate willingness or commitment towards breaking new frontiers of knowledge so much that the new knowledge must be of higher value than what used to be before, the ability of such individual or institution to initiate radical epistemic and systemic revolutions where such knowledge can be driven in direction that can respond or identify with the demands of change in a complex, globalising, pluralistic and ever-changing world, such efforts must at least be open-ended in addition to the initiators of the epistemological breakthrough showing willingness and desire to cooperate and collaborate with others who are equally interested and desirous of contributing to the growth and development of such knowledge and above all such persons and institutions must show willingness and capacity to explore, demonstrate and exhibit superlative and highest degree of critical and creative thinking (Nwaokugha & Abiakwu 2024:167).

In fact, Nwaokugha (2025:24) summarizes the above when he writes that:

There must be corresponding attitudinal dispositions on the part of an individual or individuals who show the desire, drive and enthusiasm to produce and construct knowledge and such attitudinal disposition must be one in which the individual or individuals show high levels of curiosity and readiness to the point of participating actively in the process of constructing and generating such knowledge.

Every effort at knowledge construction from the angles of social constructivism follows trajectories where such efforts must lead to improvements in the quality of life of man and trigger sustainable improvements in the functioning of institution in the society. What had been said above can be put slightly different by emphasizing that efforts at knowledge construction from the point of view of social constructivism must prioritize finding solutions to issues and challenges that impair and undermine the progressive functioning of man and his institutions.

The two theories used as theoretical frameworks for this study are suitable for the study. The use of social interdependence theory is appropriate as teaching and learning by nature are relational and constantly require innovative, dynamic, cooperative and supportive environments from the teacher and the learners where the guiding mantra can be the prevalence of an environment where the teacher and the learners are all involved together in the business of teaching and learning. The sustenance of this mutual atmosphere in teaching and learning promises a transition towards new directions in teacher education especially the development of alternative strategies in pedagogy and classroom practice, learners’ active engagement and the development of instructional roadmaps for creating insights that can guide educators, philosophers, counsellors, policy makers and planners as well as researchers on best global practices in teaching and learning. The relevance and centrality of social constructivism for this study hinges on the ability of the concept to create creative and critical insights in the members of the knowledge community or society, namely that human beings create knowledge out of their interaction and experiences in life and therefore individual and collective active participation and active engagement of all are required of all who are desirous of keeping and raising the banners and flames of knowledge to enviable heights. Unique

features, according to Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:180), which studies that adopt social constructivism as theoretical frameworks incorporate are creativity, critical thinking and critical consciousness and these easily align such studies with the qualitative or philosophical research design or methodology.

Qualitative or philosophical research design or methodology is one of the many ways of conducting researches and it is noted for its inherent features that mark it out, one of which is what Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159) call the freedom it offers to scholars and researchers to freely express and communicate their ideas to the general public on specific and general topics, a development which reveals that the philosophical or qualitative research methodology affords scholars and researchers epistemological space to investigate specific and general issues, which ordinarily may not be possible. The above position harmoniously aligns with Angadi (2019:39), who writes that the qualitative or philosophical research methodology heavily relies on the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other types of research methods.

Again one feature that is at the heart of qualitative or philosophical research methodology is that any scholar or researcher who uses it is basically the instrument for data collection, which is usually in the form of extensive narrative data and such extensive narrative data so collected must be subjected to thorough analytic scrutiny and rigours of thought that targets establishing semantic clarity and logical coherence that are necessary conditions for the establishment of knowledge in a philosophical research. Another inherent feature that is foundational and fundamental about qualitative or philosophical research method upon which it has gained receptive and widespread attention (Nwaokugha & Smith-Ogizeh, 2025:195) is noted by Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10), when they write that:

Qualitative research is exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational settings. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analysing non-numerical data such as interviews, observations, case studies and document analysis. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena.

The richness, uniqueness and robustness of qualitative or philosophical research methodology is highlighted by Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016), who write that philosophical or qualitative research methodology incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription. Earliest attempts at knowledge construction across the world recognized speculation as key in knowledge construction so much that it has been described as foundational and fundamental pillars for successful practice in science (Currie, 2021) and other disciplines, a development Gire (2020) confirms when he writes that speculation as a qualitative or philosophical research method is primordial to all experience and thinking. The ability and capacity of speculation to be primordial to all experience and thinking or to criss-cross disciplines makes the mention of speculation an interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary concept (Nwaokugha & Agbarakwe, 2024:253).

Disciplines where speculation is a necessary condition include philosophy and all its applied disciplines, social sciences and natural sciences (Nwaokugha & Smith-Ogizeh, 2025:159). Because speculation can be applied across epistemological constituencies or territories, the concept keeps adapting to different meanings, interpretations and definitions. According to Aminigo (1999) and Agulana (2011), speculation invokes a meaning that revolves around attempts to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought while Oduor (2010:97) writes that to speculate is to “wonder, conjecture, guess and to hypothesize”. In the views of Haung, Xie and Chen (2021), speculation or speculative thinking is that type of thinking about past and future possibilities which includes counterfactual thinking, pre-factual thinking and other types of thinking. Swedberg (2021:46) is of the view that speculation revolves around two main meanings, namely; (1) a risky but potentially very profitable economic activity, and (2) the making of conjectures without firm evidence.

Any curious and analytic minded person especially one who is operating from the angles of philosophy and its applied disciplines can strongly persuade the masses to understand and interpret speculation as fundamentally invoking a meaning that revolves around “a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and

logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of a philosophical discourse (Nwaokugha & Wogonwu, 2023:4) or more technically the extent in which a conclusion derives from its premise or the premise before it. There is another possible interpretation of speculation that situates it as a guide for action that targets making change a norm in the future and this is credited to Taggart (2012), who writes that speculation and speculative thinking is foundational and fundamental in providing man and his institutions platforms and behavioural dispositions for change such as new critical, creative and evaluative lens whose main purpose is to produce and generate a philosophy and philosophy of action for influencing and determining public philosophy and philosophy of life for individual members of the society and the society or state at large. The foregoing beams searchlight in the direction highlighted by Nwaokugha (2025:26) who writes that:

Speculation is synonymous with promoting curious behavioural dispositions that are supportive of conscious drives that target providing new guidance, innovation, transformation, new ways of doing things or re-examination of practices with a view to overcoming and transcending to higher levels so that quality improvements may be introduced into the practices of man and his institutions.

The above observation aligns with the age long position that man speculates in order to know more, in order to reform, transform, transcend or transition to levels that are qualitatively better than his present state or more technically a behavioural disposition which man resorts to particularly when he is confronted and challenged by situations he cannot easily grasp or understand. The above may account for why Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:63) write that speculation and speculation thinking is the epistemological navigating compass and guide for reforms, transformation and innovation in the affairs of man and his institutions.

It is important we acknowledge that the seal of speculation is on the entire world of knowledge, however those areas of knowledge that are more receptive to change and do not have universal or one-side fits all answers to questions they pose or generate are most attractive to speculation. This is why topics that revolve around metaphysics and axiology (social philosophy, ethics, aesthetics and political philosophy) can best be handled speculatively. It is also important we point out that a scholar or researcher who previously professed a particular position about a topic or subject matter can add, modify or outrightly reject what he professed earlier about the same topic or subject matter and equally no person's position on any axiological and metaphysical topic can fore-close any other person's position on the same topic or subject matter. What provides the platform and epistemological space for the shift is the phenomenon of change and the prevailing situation of a people and their state at a particular point in time. Language and logic are foundational and fundamental in speculation.

Analysis generally and analysis as a method of philosophical research is as old as man. What accounts for this is that all conscious efforts of man at knowledge construction, development and production and man's efforts to understand himself have always integrated and revolved around analysis. This is one reason why analysis has gone through radical and revolutionary trends that have ignited reforms and transformations in its nature and use in the knowledge industry and general affairs of man. Ancient philosophers such as Socrates, Plato, Aristotle etc whose contributions to the knowledge industry cannot be under-estimated initiated the process of analysis when they discussed and provided meaning of words and concepts and established that an unexamined life was not worth living, in addition to advising man to know himself.

Analysis from ages concerns itself with meaning, clarification and communication of meaning. In contemporary times, analysis especially as a philosophical research methodology is the critical examination of words, terms, concepts and propositions with the aim of projecting and making explicit meanings that are associated with such words, terms, concepts and propositions. When a word, term or concept has gone through semantic scrutiny of analysis, such word, term or concept opens itself up to semantic clarity and linguistic precision so much that every trace of ambiguity, absurdity, contradiction and meaninglessness that may be associated with such word, term or concept may be clarified for comprehension. Analysis is principally undertaken to enhance communication, cooperation and cordial

relationship or interaction among human beings and this is highlighted by Nwaokugha (2025:27) when he writes that:

The epical and phenomenal focus of analysis on clarification of meaning is deep rooted in the fact that virtually all crisis, conflicts, misunderstanding, disagreement and wars that have wreaked havoc on man and his institutions across the globe are traceable to faulty use of words, terms, concepts and propositions or faulty communication or miscommunication.

Any scholar who robustly and creatively embraces analysis in his studies is consciously on trajectories where he lays foundations for peaceful and amicable resolution of conflicts and crises, is on a voyage and expedition where he guides humanity into developing and internalizing behavioural and attitudinal dispositions that are supportive of precision in expression, logical in presentation and thoroughness of thought in thinking and these individually and collectively are recipes for national development. In fact, Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2020:180), say it all when they write that:

Intentionally, every good and right philosophical endeavour targets better communication of ideas and better clarification of concepts and where ideas and concepts are communicated and clarified with their right meanings attached to theory, they remove the possibilities of confusion in the line of human thinking, actions and communication.

The above may account for why some scholars write that analysis has become the trending practice in scholarship and academic pursuits all over the world as it has potentials to radicalize and revolutionize the world of knowledge (Nwaokugha & Rotimi-Aina, 2025: 113) and correspondingly has become a mark of intellectual sophistication (Nwaokugha & Wogonwu, 2020:180) for scholars and researchers who use it. Scholars and researchers who make analysis their destination of choice or article of faith start by doing what Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016:421) call breaking down their subject matter into smaller units that constitute it and at the same time show how all are related in attaining specific objective. Analysis is of two types namely conceptual analysis and linguistic analysis. Conceptual analysis concerns itself with ascertaining if the meaning that a concept is associated with is actually the meaning of that concept while linguistic analysis focuses on establishing if the meaning that is ascribed to a sentence is the meaning that sentence expresses or conveys. Language and logic play instrumental roles in analysis especially the establishment of relationship or connection between appearance and reality.

Every scholar and every research effort targets solving, resolving and addressing one problem or the other so that there can be quality improvements in the life of man and his institutions. The concluding section of a study or any academic discourse where scholars and researchers focus exclusive attention in the form of suggesting and recommending remedies or solutions for addressing, solving and resolving identified problems qualify as prescription (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024:64, Nwaokugha & Smith-Ogizeh, 2025:16). The above is simplified by Oduor (2010:97), who writes that “to prescribe is to recommend or set down as a rule or guide” and how this can be put into practical reality is highlighted by Nwaokugha (2021:102) who writes that prescription:

Is achieved in research in the form of a researcher making autonomous value statement on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be solved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed. In this way, suggestions and recommendation in researches and other forms of writing fall within the frame of reference of prescription.

True, every scholar and researcher who is desirous of addressing, solving and resolving one problem or the other prescribes. As obvious as this fact can be, there are disciplines and scholars who by the nature of their disciplines and areas of specialization indulge more in prescription than other disciplines and scholars. Scholars in such disciplines as axiology (ethics, aesthetics, social philosophy and political philosophy) prescribe so as to be relevant and impactful in the society and why this is so is that they are guided by the trend of events or changes in the society in prescribing what they prescribe to the members of the society.

The use of the philosophical research methodology is phenomenally excellent for this study and this derives justifications from the fact that teaching and learning as human activities undertaken by the

teacher in complex and ever-changing global village epically benefits from philosophy and philosophical reflections. The inclination and commitment of philosophy and philosophical reflections to creating insights help to deepen and sharpen scholars' and researchers' creative and critical insights, curiosity and investigative skills that results in widening and broadening the frontiers of knowledge, a development that in addition to building scholars' and researchers' epistemological, metaphysical and axiological confidence levels in their pursuit and construction of knowledge, radically and revolutionally develops die-hard and resilient spirits in scholars and researchers in the form of researchers and scholars re-examining, repositioning, reforming and transforming themselves into developing insights for seeing challenges and developments in the education industry and outside the education industry as doable, solvable and resolvable. One quality revolution which has implications for progress and sustainable human survival that the creative and critical insights which philosophy and philosophical research methodology has brought into the education industry is the spirit of collaboration, which according to Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:168),

results in the breaking of new frontiers of knowledge as through it researchers and scholars summon up courage to investigate areas of knowledge which ordinarily are unmentionable and un-contemplatable and finally as the use of the philosophical research methodology engineers epistemological revolutions that trigger phenomenal breakthroughs in knowledge, man's quality of life receives quality improvements through opening of more opportunities for man to benefit from his investments in research and education. A trend in scholarship and research especially for studies that employ the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is to focus in detail on key concepts that are the focus of the study and to this we now turn.

Teaching:

Teaching as a concept is one in which there is a plethora of definitions or simply a riot of definitions and interpretations and that teaching receives this scholarly attention in the education industry and instructional space may be pointing in directions that teaching foundationally and fundamentally is central and critical to achieving the dreams of the individual and those of the state in the forms of helping to ensure quality human capital development, stability, social reforms and social transformations in the affairs of man and his institutions. Teaching is instrumental for the national and sustainable developments of states. Unique to such definitions and interpretations by scholars and institutions is the fact that every scholar and institution provides a unique definition of teaching that receptively and robustly expands the scope of the concept. According to Okoh (2003:71), "teaching is the conscious and deliberate effort by mature or experienced person to impart information, knowledge, skills and so on to an immature or less experienced person with the intention that the latter will learn or come to believe what he is taught on good grounds". Adding to the above, Sequeira (2012) writes that teaching is a set of events, outside the learner which are designed to support internal process of learning.

Anyone who takes a critical and insightful look at the above definitions of teaching can come to the realization that many things are involved in teaching and many things can be realized from teaching. It can be strongly deduced that teaching is at the heart of any impactful and meaningful human capital development project of any state and its people and that teaching is at the centre of any conscious and systematic efforts of any state to convert or transform her citizens from a lower to a higher level of consciousness so that the citizens can identify and align themselves with the aspirations and visions of the state. It can also be said or established that teaching is basically a relational, communicative and interactive activity between a teacher and learners, where the mission of the teacher is to professionally present facts (that is, content or information to learners) and expect a systematic feedback from his learners, primarily in a definitive and definable classroom setting, which on its own can have certain aesthetic features that are structured to motivate and stimulate the curiosity of the learners to learn. What had been said above can further be stepped down to imply that teaching is a goal oriented task that is undertaken by the teacher, who has received professional education in the art of teaching and consequently doubles as a mature and experienced person whose professional education equips with

knowledge and skills to positively influence, impact knowledge, facts and information to a less experienced and immature person with the intent that the less experienced and less mature person can learn and be reformed and transformed along lines where the less experienced and less mature person becomes a better person for his individual growth and development and the advancement of his society or state.

We need to point out that what is consciously and unconsciously done in the process of teaching by the teacher systematically leads to two key developments namely learning and education and we also need to note that teaching revolves around a teacher, learners, and a content or a subject matter. All these take place in an ideal environment called a classroom and a proof that learning has taken place in an individual is the demonstration and manifestation of positive changes in the life of the individual learner and such positive change may include ability to resolve conflicts, make quality contributions to ideas that can lead to human development and the ability to indulge in creative and critical thinking. A demonstration of all the above either singularly or in combination is a recipe for development. Anyone with an analytic insight can strongly say that teaching is a cluster or a conglomerate of actions and activities performed by the teacher that facilitates learning and education in learners on one hand and human capital development on the other. The multiple and many context in which the functions of teaching can apply makes teaching a polymorphous concept (Okoh, 2003), no wonder Rajagopalan (2019:5) writes that:

Teaching is regarded as both an art and science. As an art, it lays stress on the imaginative and artistic abilities of the teacher in creating a worthwhile situation in the classroom to enable student to learn. As a science, it sheds light on the logical, mechanical or procedural steps to be followed to attain an effective achievement of goals.

Teaching does not occur in a vacuum rather it occurs in a multi-complex setting where virtually all the stakeholders lack full control of the situation and where events and activities occur simultaneously, requiring instant judgements and defying predictions. What is exposed above is that teaching occurs in a complex and unpredictable setting and the man who initiate all actions and activities in this complex and unpredictable learning space whose actions, intrigues, tricks and manoeuvres, trigger in learners the enthusiasm and curiosity to learn is the teacher. The crucial role and the centrality of the teacher in any impactful and meaningful teaching learning situation has been highlighted by Nwaokugha (2014:14) when he writes that the teacher is “the man who sits in the driver’s seat and creates the necessary environment that facilitates teaching and learning”.

In the teaching learning situation, the teacher function at different levels, prominent among which include functioning;

as a bridge builder between learners and parents, between educational institutions and other institutions of the state. Teachers traditionally issue evaluation reports on learners, which institutions rely upon in placing learners for jobs in their establishments and teachers issue referrals which assist other professionals in the effective discharge of their duties. (Nwaokugha, 2014:14-15).

The teacher is so important in the creative and complex art of teaching and learning so much that he is the central figure in the implementation of all reforms and innovations in education. It is upon his commitment and dedication to duty that any meaningful and impactful success can be achieved in education and on the other hand, any compromise on issues that revolve around him such as lack of dedication, not being committed, not adequate in number, not adequately taken care of in terms of payment of salaries and other incentives and lacking in basic and foundational qualifications are direct invitations for failure irrespective of any personality or institution backing such policies, programmes, changes and innovations. What attests to the crucial and critical roles of the teacher in the education industry is the global recognition and acknowledgement as endorsed in the national education policy documents of most state, including Nigeria that “no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers” (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004).

One fact that must be acknowledged and recognized about teaching and the teacher is that teaching is a complex, difficult and strenuous activity that exposes the teacher on a daily basis to complex challenges. A fundamental challenge that teachers face in the line of their statutory duties in the classroom and the

school is the complex and multifaceted composition of learners. Learners in one classroom and in one school come from different socio-economic backgrounds and bring into the classroom and the school different value systems that in most cases stimulate unhealthy relationships among learners in the classroom and in the school including making learners demonstrate behaviours that violate globally established rules and regulations for effective and productive administration and management of classroom and by extension the schools. Equally the heterogeneous backgrounds of learners in the classroom and in the school easily introduce cultural and religious sentiments and biases in the classroom and in the school that pose serious challenges in the line of duty of the teacher.

Another serious challenge which teachers face globally that has become a critical source of their frustration and demotivation is the social status of the teacher in the society. Teaching is acknowledged as being the noblest profession but realities from history and in contemporary times situate teaching and its practitioners in the category of the most looked down profession and its practitioners among the poorest of the poor, who equally demonstrate and manifest the highest form of powerlessness and general professional disenchantment so much that many teachers continuously look for other employment and those who persist to remain in the profession cannot come closer to those learners they taught in terms of accumulation of wealth, property, affluence and influence in the society. The cumulative effect of these challenges is that most practitioners do not wish their sons and daughters to become teachers and teaching is fast becoming an option that learners apply for only when they cannot secure admission in choice or other preferred professions. In fact, teaching is a profession whose practitioners are in reverse gear in all indexes for measuring progress and social mobility. Teachers are not being cared for by those who employ them and the consequence of this is that hardship is higher among them and members of their families. Teachers do not enjoy any iota of respect or social prestige from the members of the society and teachers are phenomenally stripped of power so much that decisions that concern their immediate constituency are imposed on them from above without their inputs. Most states especially in developing and underdeveloped countries are least committed to human capital development of their states and these states demonstrate their lack of commitment to human capital development through a systemic lack of investments in the education industry in which teachers are the first direct and indirect victims. As a proof of this, some states owe teacher salaries and other incentives for years and teachers more than any other professionals work in most dehumanizing environments where the right infrastructure may not be available.

Learning

Learning is one concept in which psychologists, philosophers and educators pay so much attention to and why this is so is that man by nature has in-built mechanisms to master, control, cope, adapt and understand any environment in which he finds himself. At any point in time the efforts of man to master, control, adapt and understand his environment translates into reality or results to sustainable, superlative and qualitative improvement, what has resulted or unfolded is learning. As obvious as this can be, learning as a concept is fluid and what accounts for its fluidity is that learning falls within the brackets of concept that are very difficult to define in clear and precise terms. This exposition points in the direction that learning is a polymorphous concept and this insight that learning is a polymorphous concept is acknowledged by Tabacaru (2019), who writes that the meaning of learning signals and invokes dual semantic trajectories namely; “one to understand the past and one to predict the future”.

Deriving from the above, different scholars and institutions define learning from their idiosyncratic perspectives where a point emphasized by one scholar may not be emphasized by another scholar. Learning especially human learning according to Bandura (1962) usually take place by observing the consequences of model behaviour while learning according to Skinner (1957) is the formation of new behaviour. Gagne (1974) sees learning as invoking a meaning that revolves around changes in human capacity that can be sustainably maintained, which however cannot be attributed to growth processes. In his own definition of learning Woodworth (1945) writes that any activity can be called learning so far it

develops the individual and makes him alter behaviour and experiences different from what he or she would otherwise have been.

Anyone who critically looks at the above definitions of learning can admit that the meaning of learning revolves around one central focus namely; observable, intentional and purposeful change in the behaviour of an individual that occurs after an experience. This accounts for why the commonest definition of learning is that it is a relatively permanent change in the life of an individual that is traceable to experience and not to growth or maturational processes.

Learning is unique in the sense that it has inherent features that can enable any right thinking individual to differentiate who has acquired it from who has not required it. Learning is a process that leads to the acquisition of knowledge where anyone who is curious and desirous of possessing it must show some level of commitment and dedication to its pursuit. The pursuit of learning is one axiological pursuit that is central to man and this is so simply because learning is foundational and fundamental for the survival of man and his institutions and correspondingly investment in learning is the pivot and guiding compass for engineering and initiating any revolutionary and radical changes for driving the society in positive directions.

What triggers and stimulates learning is curiosity, creativity, critical consciousness and experience and for the experience of an individual or individuals who claim to have gone through the process of learning to practically and realistically qualify in the right sense of the concept, such experiences must have capacities and potentials to reform, transform, radically, clinically and revolutionally change the individual, individuals and the world for the better. In practice, learning maintains a hierarchical order where what is to be learnt is presented to the learners in a manner where the presenter, presumably the teacher presents or starts with low-level facts about the topic or subject matter to be learnt and learners proceed to higher level facts about the same topic in question. This is what in everyday language is called starting from the known to the unknown or from simple to complex. It has to be pointed out that in learning, the ability of the learners to excel or make sense in the higher level facts is highly dependent on the extent in which the learners have been proficient in the low level facts or how they have gained mastery of the low level facts, which they had been earlier exposed to. Again, anyone who is desirous and curious of learning must show such readiness and willingness by actively engaging in making meaning of the learning experiences he has been engaged in, must participate and contribute through engaging and collaborating with others who equally show willingness to learn and the learner must personally take responsibility for learning.

What had been said above can be expanded by maintaining that to make meaning by the learner demands him to connect and link whatever knowledge he has gained in the past to his new learning, be bold to communicate his ideas and perspectives and let such lead to his participation in co-creating and co-constructing learning experiences or lead to developing workable and pragmatic learning formula that can be beneficial to humanity. In fact, one who is desirous of learning must show commitment, determined, must be self-disciplined to the point of directing himself and initiating actions that are conducive and supportive of learning.

Learning is a lifelong process which can hardly be exhausted or completed. It is foundational and fundamental to note that the tasks of learning lies with the learner, who must show capacity, determination, seriousness and commitment to the process of learning. The index for determining if a learner has actually gone through the process of learning is the extent in which he can receptively indulge in habits and behaviours that are reflections of positive change in behaviour as well as his development of cognitive capacities that are supportive of ability to think autonomously, including the demonstration of creative and critical thinking abilities. The task of the teacher in the whole process is to create the conducive and supportive learning environment that can support and promote the active engagement and active participation of the learner. In all of these, any objective evaluation of educational institutions across the globe can quickly come to the conclusion that the reality in teaching and learning occasioned by the different backgrounds of the learners, the unpredictability of events in the classroom, the simultaneous occurrence of actions and activities in the classroom, poor learning conditions, lack of

infrastructure in schools and the different expectations from individuals (learners, parents and the state) make the classroom and the school not too rosy for achieving the core mandate of education for the teachers, learners, parents and the state and therefore make cooperation between the teacher and the learners inevitable.

Cooperation

The universe is a system whose make-up, build up, structure and composition is robustly, phenomenally and excellently fascinating and people who understand the universe as such quickly invest, harness and explore its riches and correspondingly achieve their mission across all areas of their endeavours. The systematic dynamics upon which they succeed in their endeavours and actions are their conscious inclination to leveraging on cooperation. In fact, conscious breakthroughs that are derived from the application or exploration of man's intellectual capacity or intellectual instincts that step down into harmoniously addressing and resolving one issue or the other or that lead to revolutions that trigger quality innovations that sustainably add value by improving the quality of life of man or simply bring sustainable stability into the affairs of man and institutions of the state can only be possible where there is cooperation.

The insight and awareness that cooperation is a necessary condition for human progress, the survival of man, his institutions and the state situates cooperation in the centre of actions and activities and a focal flashpoint in contemporary discourse across disciplines so much that it is at the centre of multi-disciplinary, interdisciplinary and cross disciplinary studies and researches. In the light of the above observation, Brennam and Sayre-McCord (2018), write that cooperation is a term that is common in social sciences (economics and political science), in humanities especially moral philosophy and political theory as well as evolutionary biology. It is also important to note that cooperation is also key in administration and management sciences as well as the various fields of engineering especially computer engineering, software engineering, system engineering, structural engineering and artificial systems engineering. To be expected of a concept in the frame of reference as indicated above can be the possibility of a plethora of definitions and interpretations from scholars and researchers, each highlighting context specific meanings and interpretations that may not be contained in the definition and interpretation provided by another scholar and researcher.

Cooperation according to Gardner, Griffin and West (2009) is any adaptation that has evolved, at least in part, to increase the productive success of the actor's social partners from another perspective. Khamis, Kamel and Salichs (n.d) write that linguistically, cooperation refers to the practise of people or entities working together with commonly agreed upon goals and possibly methods, instead of working separately in competition while Cittolin (2018:28) defines cooperation as a social practice that brings individuals together in search of complementarity of interest. Cooperation can also be defined from perspectives where focus is not on actions and activities of human beings but on non-human beings. According to Khamis et al (n.d), cooperation can also be defined as the practice of hardware and/or software entities working together in order to achieve certain objectives.

Anyone who has the least sense of critical analysis or critical consciousness can attest to the fact that cooperation in all its multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary nature invokes a meaning that supports and promotes developments where individuals in a bargain or transaction prioritize relationships, association, dialogue, interaction, embrace or make working together a norm, cordially and harmoniously working with one another, working jointly and making quality and meaningful contributions for the attainment of common interests and collective goals that can result in mutual benefits for all the parties in a bargain or transaction. It is correct to say that the *modus operandi* of cooperation is one in which individuals deemphasize or play down competition but alternatively prioritize interaction with individuals and associative relationship and through this line of behaviour mutually discuss, mutual evaluate and mutually provide answers and solutions to common problems that can be beneficial to all the individual who are involved in a bargain or transaction through collective actions that can be of great benefit to all.

What unfolds where behaviours that are conducive and supportive of cooperation are initiated is the consciousness and awareness that the survival of individuals in the society is strongly hinged on social interdependence especially positive social interdependence, a development that points in the direction that individuals need one another to excel, to achieve their objectives and to be successful in bargains or transactions and the individuals who are desirous of initiating behaviours that are conducive and supportive of cooperation must demonstrate a sense of commitment, sense of responsibility and above all learn to protect the interests of others as they equally protect their own in a bargain or transaction. On the other hand, an individual's well-orchestrated and well-focused action and behaviours can translate to nothing where others in the same environment refuse to cooperate with him. This gives a strong support that no matter how strong, how educated, how influential, how clever, how intelligent, how handsome or how beautiful an individual can be, the individual needs the cooperation of others in the same environment or locality with him before he can maximally make any meaningful development, implying that the success or failure of an individual is systematically tied and connected to how other individuals in the same environment or locality cooperate with him.

In any bargain, transaction or institution where cooperation has come to stay, such setting has potentials to consciously initiate revolutions where citizens can achieve their individual and common goals for the common good of humanity, can lay foundations for setting up mechanism for avoiding or reducing the occurrence of conflicts to their barest minimum, can make division of labour a priority among citizens as citizens specialize in areas of their interests, can bring in or trigger reforms and transformations that can radically and revolutionally put in place mechanisms for collective decision making that can be conducive and supportive of democracy and good governance, can set in motion a culture and tradition that can favour the growth of knowledge and knowledge dissemination that are necessary triggers for national development and above all, any society where the citizens internalize the virtues and values of cooperation can consciously be instilling in the citizens a robust culture and tradition of collective intelligence where the wisdom of an individual can be beneficial to other members of his society. These receptive developments and revolutions that are associated with cooperation are epical testimonies that cooperation is the foundation upon which human civilization and sustainable national development of any state is based or can be based. We can say and say it very strongly that cooperation is the inherent framework upon which survival of natural species depends and species that cooperate can achieve results that are beyond expectations. Any curious minded individual can notice that lower species or creatures execute and carry out intelligent and unimaginable tasks by virtue of their ability to work cooperatively. The Bible book of Proverbs Chapter 6:6-9 draws attention to this when it calls on man to:

Go to the ants, you sluggard,
Consider its ways and be wise
It has no commander
No overseer or ruler
Yet it stores its provisions in summer
And gathers its food at harvest.
How long will you lie there?
You sluggard

Acknowledgement of the power of cooperation among individual lower creatures is further highlighted and in details in Proverbs 30:24-28 in these words:

Four things on earth are small, yet they are extremely wise:

Ants are creatures of little strength, yet they store up their food in the summer,

Coneys are creatures of little power, yet they make their homes in the crags,

Locusts have no kings yet they advance together in ranks, a lizard can be caught with the hand yet it is found in kings' palaces.

What can be deduced philosophically speaking is that nothing can be impossible for people or creatures that make cooperation their guiding principle and article of faith and with cooperation comes wisdom and the ability to overcome and conquer challenges.

True, cooperation can be applied, adopted or adapted in all areas of human endeavours but one area where it is excessively receptive to is in the area of human capital development, which is the core concern of teaching and learning or precisely education. It is a fact that teaching and learning is synonymous with manifesting variables in which the teacher and the learners, two critical stakeholders in the education industry do not and cannot have control over. However, as obvious as it is that variables which the teacher and the learners have no control over them are ever present in teaching and learning situations, teachers can maximally deliver their instructions and learners can maximally benefit from such instructions if both the teacher and the learners embrace cooperation in the complex task of teaching and learning. In fact, the teacher and the learner in the complex task of teaching and learning can initiate meaningful cooperation for the attainment and realization of the objectives of education and national development of states. How this can be possible is the focus of the next section of the paper.

Pragmatic Steps for Promoting Cooperation between the Teacher and Learners in Teaching and Learning Situations.

What learners, teachers, parents and the state expect education to accomplish for humanity is sophisticated, inclusive, complex and comprehensive. The level of complexity and sophistication of the expectations of the individual and those of the society demands new narratives and strategies for solving and resolving them and one focal flashpoint and direction in this new thinking is a conscious drive and paradigm shift that can prioritize making cooperation a norm between the teacher and the learners in the instructional craft of teaching and learning. Part of the justification for prioritizing cooperation in teaching and learning between the teacher and the learner is the fact that the education industry is an instructional space that flourishes on continuous development of innovations and the new innovative directions canvassed in this study can be said to be in-breed, unlike most innovations in teaching and learning or education generally that are imposed on teachers and learners. In fact, making cooperation between the teacher and the learners a norm in teaching and learning has potentials to reform and transform education and by extension humanity through introducing and laying foundations for new beginnings whose entry into the education space can spring up policies, reforms and transformations that can specifically derive from critical stakeholders in education, the teacher and the learners as against the current system where policies and practices are imposed on the teacher and the learners from above.

Teaching is basically a relational activity and correspondingly cooperation and collaboration are at the centre. As a relational concept, teaching demands that the teacher and the learners work cooperatively and collaboratively together for the attainment of predetermined and anticipated results that are of common interests to the teacher, the learners and the society generally. In this case, what is of concern and interest to the teacher and the learners in discussions that are focused on cooperation in teaching and learning is the creation of supportive relational and conducive environments that can promote motivation or curiosity and consequently enhance the presentation of instruction by the teacher that can equally result in higher and quality learning by the learners. Creating a conducive relational and supportive environment by a teacher is the first logical step in promoting cooperation in a teaching learning situation and this insight may have prompted da Luz (2015:2) to note that the best productivity in a classroom comes from effective cooperation between the teacher and the students.

Anyone who critically scrutinizes what obtains in teaching learning situations can quickly admit that much responsibilities lie with the teacher in the business of promoting cooperation between him and the learners. Having recognized this, the next point of call in promoting cooperation between the teacher and the learners lies in conscious and systematic efforts in developing and upgrading the quality of instructions, the teacher receives in the course of his teacher education programmes. During the teacher's education programmes, the teacher can be educated along lines where emphasis and priority can be on the teacher demonstrating and becoming sympathetic, empathetic, accommodating and combine same with

strong leadership qualities and influence that can enable him develop in learners the capacity for positive interdependence. These are necessary because the teacher in all ramifications is an authority and a role model whose dispositions have a lot to do in terms of promoting cooperation between him and his learners. We can say it with all amount of assurance that teachers who show positive attitudinal dispositions have all it takes to promote, influence and trigger in learners a corresponding reciprocal attitude of cooperation in teaching learning situations through fostering supportive and conducive environments by means of clearly defined, articulated and well mapped out behavioral expectations and changes he (the teacher) expects from learners.

As the teacher is the manager of the classroom, he holds the key to igniting and making sure there is cooperation in the classroom between him and the learners. He, the teacher is the starting point for initiating behaviors that are supportive and conducive of cooperation in the classroom and he can achieve this through his professional dispositions. Realistically, the teacher must demonstrate behaviours that are inclusive, accommodating and supportive of the speed of the learning abilities and learning needs of every learner in his classroom. A teacher who is supportive according to da Luz (2015:2)

Is one who creates efficiently a positive classroom environment, who encourages students to behave well and be motivated. Supportive teachers are also teachers who emphasize the learning process by giving all students the chance to construct their learning and be engaged with the content.

Part of what has been revealed from the above remarks is that the teacher who has capacity to initiate cooperation with his learners in the classroom must be an expert in pedagogy, so proficient that he can sustainably switch his methods of teaching to accommodate, carry every learner along and make rooms for interactions between him and his learners to learn from one another. A teacher who achieves the above can raise and skyrocket the curiosity and motivation levels of his learners and a corresponding behaviour from his learners will naturally be one of full cooperation and its concomitant engagement, commitment and devotion to the learning process, a development that has potentials to make the learners active in the learning process.

The ability of the teacher to create a supportive learning environment, develop supportive cordial relationships with his learners, act as role model, exert and foster transformative influence on his learners and be an expert in instructional delivery are all sure strategies for promoting cooperation between a teacher and his learners but what mostly triggers or stimulates in learners attitudinal dispositions upon which they can cooperate with the teacher in teaching learning sessions in the classroom are the learners' objective assessments of the teacher, especially on such moral indexes as a teacher's level of trust, ability to respect himself as well as the learners, truthfulness, punctuality, dedication and commitment to duties, tolerance, sense of justice and judgement, practical demonstration of care and love for learners under his care and the extent in which the teacher stands in or plays the role of the parents of learners in his classroom. A teacher who builds and develops confidence in his learners as well as provides guidance can have his efforts paid back or reciprocated in the form of cooperation the learners can exhibit or demonstrate in the classroom in the course of teaching and learning. One fact that cannot be disputed is the recognition that learners are critical stakeholders in teaching and learning and in the entire education industry, and who are ever ready to cooperate with teachers who show professional expertise through creating the right relational and supportive environments in the course of teaching and learning in the classroom.

CONCLUSION

The knowledge industry in the 21st century has excessively and phenomenally expanded in policy, programmes, practices, methods of pedagogy, contents, scope and ways of attaining them so much that many strategies and innovations have found their ways into the education industry. The guiding philosophy of the innovations is to improve and enhance productivity both on the part of the teacher and on the part of the learners, bearing in mind that teaching and learning has continuously suffered many deficits and deficiencies especially in developing and under developed states. Part of how deficits and deficiencies have become norms in teaching and learning is that most innovations in teaching and

learning are synonymous with top-down paradigms instead of a paradigm shift that prioritizes a bottom-up approach. The continuous imposition of innovations and practices from the top into the classroom is one reason why the system stifles critical thinking, creativity and productivity among teachers and learners and also a notable reason why teaching and learning suffers and will continue to suffer phenomenal neglect. It can be said with all amount of boldness that the neglect of teaching and learning correspondingly leaves indelible negative impressions on human capital building and the national development of states. It is correct that these not-too-good behaviours in the education industry directly and indirectly rubbishes and demotivates the teacher and learners, two critical stakeholders in the education industry from making impactful, meaningful and quality contributions to the development of the education industry.

These developments that are triggered by a top down paradigms and their trickle down effects on human capital building and national development of states, notwithstanding, there is a general consensus and a general awareness that teaching and learning is the hub upon which the national development of states depends and there is also a consensus that there is urgent need for a bottom up approach to innovations in teaching and learning where priority can be on promoting cooperation between the teacher and the learners in teaching and learning in the classroom.

Promoting cooperation between the teacher and the learners as a pedagogical innovations in teaching and learning is a welcome development and the critical stakeholders in education upon which its success depends are the teacher education institutions, the teachers and the learners. Teacher education institutions can redesign teacher education programmes and in the new outlook prioritize developing courses that can focus on how teachers and their learners can work together for the attainment of a common goal, bearing in mind that the ability of a teacher to succeed in a classroom largely depends on how cooperative the learners can be. Equally, teacher education institutions can have it at the back of their minds that presently, majority of the teachers in the teaching profession do not have knowledge of the right behavioural and attitudinal dispositions that are conducive for and supportive of cooperation in teaching and learning in the classroom. This is an open challenge and an open invitation to teacher education institutions, a challenge they can explore by creating the right awareness and sensitizing the government and all appropriate agencies or bodies charged with such responsibilities so that they can mount in-service and refresher courses for such teachers on one hand as well as sensitize teacher education institutions to shed off their excessive conservatism and unreceptive attitudes to change by thinking far through aligning teacher education to current realities in a complex and globalising world where change occurs in a split second order. This means the teacher has to play down on his ego by developing a personality that can give all his learners a sense of belonging. Teacher education institutions has to tailor the education of the teacher along this line. This line of thinking is deeply rooted in moral rationality where the teacher and the learners can see themselves as people who are working together for the attainment of one common goal. Any attempt by the teacher or the learner to introduce undesirable behaviours into the teaching learning environment can be detrimental to the two persons, in addition to being strange as no right thinking person works against himself. To this end, the teacher and learners in the classroom must sustain and maintain relational, supportive, caring and conducive environment for their mutual interests in the teaching learning environment.

For sure, teachers who make cooperation norms in their professional practice can professionally improve themselves, by becoming more impactful to their learners and the society as well as take the teaching profession to the next level. On the other hand, teachers who work cooperatively with their learners will receive exponential, epical and phenomenal cooperation from their learners and the teaching job for such teachers can be one that is full of positive emotions. Therefore, this is a pedagogical innovation that has potentials to improve the teacher and the teaching profession.

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